
RESEARCH ARTICLE

Enhancing Motivation and Developing Positive Attitudes in an ESP Context

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ABSTRACT

ESP has been enriched by many theoretical inputs, but ESP itself does not have any universally accepted theory. From primary to tertiary, second/ foreign language English teaching/ learning depends on the motivation and attitude toward the target language. The present article outlines the theoretical foundation of an English for Specific Purpose (ESP) writing course, which was designed, implemented and assessed to enhance the proficiency of English writing skills of engineering students in six colleges under MAKAUT in West Bengal. India tops the world in terms of the number of engineering students and colleges. To meet engineering students' academic and workplace writing needs, the most important requirement is a writing course. Implementing the ESP course required multi-dimensional theoretical considerations drawn from areas like ESP, needs analysis, theories of language and language learning, syllabus design, motivation and attitude, and writing as a language skill. In this study, the theoretical underpinnings applied in classroom teaching related to enhancing motivation and improving attitude are discussed. The difference in the mean, median and mode scores with regards to pre and post writing tests and highly positive student feedback on materials, methodology, techniques, and sub components of writing skill indicated a significant improvement and established the efficacy of such an eclectic approach, which can be used in subsequent ESP course designs.

KEYWORDS

ESP, motivation, attitude, classroom implementation, writing course, engineering students

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1. Introduction

This research was part of my dissertation work. To design and implement a new writing course for first-year engineering students from six colleges in West Bengal, an elaborate needs analysis was carried out. The views of the engineering students, the ESP (English for Specific Purpose) teachers, and the professional engineers (both operational and managerial) were taken, and an attempt was made to align the views of all these stakeholders to make the writing course of the classroom to reflect as much and as far as possible the professional needs of the engineers. At any stage, motivation and attitude are important factors in learning and individual differences. Any teaching/ learning should be preceded by enhancement of the motivation levels and proper tuning of the positive attitude toward ESP teaching/ learning. The present article highlights the theories identified to enhance motivation and make the attitude of students more positive toward ESP writing. The connection with workplace needs and requirements was shared with students so that they knew what they were doing and why.

1.1. The uniqueness of ESP

Saber (2016) considers English for specific purposes (ESP) as a category in a specific social context based on professional or content-related issues. (p.2) Pettit's seminal work in 2002 has led Sarré and Whyte (2017) to include the study of discourse features and culture of a specific group of professionals along with the didactic study of language learning and teaching within ESP. (p. 150).

Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) argue that the chief distinguishing features of ESP are needs and text analysis, and consequently gravitating toward learning for communicating effectively in the classroom and workplace. (p.1). Hutchinson and Waters (2009) first claim that ESP is not any "particular" language, "methodology", or "material" and conclude that it is an approach which has as its fundamental defining characteristic of learner needs. (p. 19). However, from all the definitions above, the narrow focus of ESP is proven.

1.1.1 ESP versus EGP/ELP

ESP is different from English for General Purpose (EGP) because an ESP is associated with a particular field, such as medicine, engineering, and business. Its usage is primarily linked to employment and academic objectives. ESP is more in demand for engineering students than EGP in academic and workplace requirements because of its focus and time-saving outlook.

ESP is a learning method that focuses primarily on students' needs. Beyond classroom activities, an ESP instructor, as per Hutchinson and Waters (2009, pp. 22-23), needs to undertake needs analysis, design of the syllabuses, writing materials or modifications, and evaluations. The second significant distinction is that an ESP instructor must be trained with the desired ESP orientation.

ESP and English Language Teaching (ELT) are not at loggerheads. Past simple passive learning while writing laboratory reports is used elsewhere as well throughout life. ESP is simply more focused and narrower in range when compared to ELT. (Barnard & Zemach, 2003, pp. 306--307). ESP, as well as ELT, strive for communicative competence.

However, there are crucial differences between the two. Specific ESP courses are more limited in their aims compared to general English courses, and so learners are likely to be more motivated towards them. ELT deals with the issues as to where, when, and why language is needed, in other words, as "situated language use" while ESP, for most parts, deals with the usage of language. (Basturkmen, 2010, p. 8). ESP generally deals with certain, specific domains of language which the ordinary or general language user does not need. (Tudor, 1997, p. 91). General English often moves from the point of start to a "pretty indeterminate destination" whereas ESP moves from the same starting point to a known destination. (Basturkmen, 2014, p. 9).

1.2 Motivation, Attitude, and Second Language Acquisition

Of all the factors that aid in language learning, motivation remains one of the most important (Dörnyei et al., 2006; Gardner, 2010). If motivation is high, it leads to a larger number of strategies being employed and more time allocated by the learner along with his/ her aptitude, leading to the maximization of his/ her learning potential. (Stansfield & Winke, 2008, p. 83). Ellis (2009) states that no single factor of individual differences has received as much attention as motivation.

Motivation is a notoriously evasive term, and it has been variously defined in psychology and other social sciences. Dörnyei (1998) accepts the difficulty of defining this construct. (p.117). It is an extremely broad term, and it encompasses various concepts and ideas within it. (Dörnyei, 2001, p. 7).

However, here we will take the definition of Gardner (1985) to start with as far as language learning/ESP is concerned. As per Gardner (1985), motivation encompasses three factors: effort, desire and affect. Effort implies the time given to achieve the goal; desire refers to how strong the urge is; affect implies the response or attitude of the learner towards language learning as a whole and to the sub-parts of it.

Though attitude is also an umbrella term, it may still be defined as the natural inclination to respond to any attitude object favourably or unfavourably. (Oskamp & Schultz, 2005, p. 9). Stern et al. (1983) claim that for language learning, the affective component has a larger part to play than the cognitive component. Gardner (1985) links motivation and attitude because the former is only possible when there is an effort to learn the language. Attitude and motivation both complement each other, and both contain within themselves the traces of the other. (Gardner, 1985, p. 31).

1.3 Motivational theories and their application

There are many constructs and theories related to motivation and attitude because of their importance. However, this study focused on three main theories- Gardner's (1985) socio-psychological model, Krashen's (2009) affective filter hypothesis, Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) and Dörnyei and Ushioda's (2009) L2 motivational self-system and the classroom techniques suggested by Dörnyei (2001) to raise the motivation of the learners. (p.29).

1.3.1 Gardner's (1985) socio-psychological model

Gardner brings a socio-psychological perspective to motivation. The main kind of motivation is integrative, that is, the intention to become a valued member of the group that is proficient in the language. (Gardner, 1985). However, this concept can run into

rough weather if the learner has only one language to learn. There is also the instrumental category, though not as pronounced as the integrative one in his study. Instrumental implies practical considerations for learning a language, for example, getting a high grade in a test exam, scholarship, or promotion in the workplace. He finds a strong connection between integrative motivation and attitudes, which he considers as a reaction to the environment, which includes the materials, methods, courses, and teachers.

1.3.1.1 Application in ESP teaching.

The teacher shared with the learners in all possible ways the likely gains that the learners could make by learning the target language. As native speakers were not available, pictures, videos, and the voices of the native speakers were introduced to the non-- native learners.

1.3.2 Krashen's (2009) affective filter hypothesis

Krashen (2009) lays utmost importance on affective filters (or attitudinal variables like "motivation", "self-confidence", and "anxiety" in "second language acquisition". (p.31) These are crucial factors, and hence, he argues that because of differences in affective filters, learning varies from learner to learner even though the input remains the same. Attitudes need to be at a premium because only then more input will be demanded, and they will have a "lower or weaker filter" (Krashen, 2009, p.31), thereby maximizing the learning potential. The opposite will also be true. Negative attitudes will lead to a lesser desire for input and a higher or stronger filter. So, for desired acquisition, not only does sufficient comprehensible input need to be provided, but also the affective filter should be lower. (Krashen, 2009, pp. 30--32).

1.3.2.1 Application in ESP Teaching.

The classroom environment was fun-filled, non-threatening, and anxiety-free. As anxiety could be caused by communication with others, tests, and negative feedback, these were considerably reduced, particularly in the initial stages. Feedback was more on the generic side than on the specific one. However, individual feedback was also provided, but only in one-to-one sessions with the concerned learner. The learners were given time to respond when they wanted to, and there was not any hurry in early production. Error correction was handled carefully because negative feedback, particularly in the presence of others, could result in negative attitudes toward language, the language learning environment, and the teacher.

1.3.3 Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) and Dörnyei and Ushioda's (2009) L2 motivational self-system.

Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014, pp.11-14) and Dörnyei and Ushioda (2009) have proposed their "L2 motivational self-system" consisting of (a) "the ideal selves," (b) "the ought-to selves" and (c) the "L2 learning experience".

The ideal L2 self is the ideal condition that one wishes/dreams /hopes to reach. The ideal picture of the native speaker/ expert will spur the learner to reduce the gap between his present state and the ideal state of the future. Thus, this component shows its affinity to the intrinsic and integrative motivation of Gardner (1985).

The ought-to L2 self-emphasizes what others (family, friends, teachers, etc.) expect the learner to achieve. It is a sort of societal pressure or expectation. Fulfilling the wishes of people who matter a lot in life pulls the trigger for learning to reach the point where the important others want the learner to be.

The last category comprises the experience of and attitude of the learner toward the external factors of learning, which include the teacher, peers, curriculum, materials, and methodology.

Further, Dörnyei's model (2001, p.29) provided an elaborate description of how to raise the motivation of the learners through classroom teaching. In this model, there are four cyclic steps/ stages to be followed by the teacher in the classroom – "creating", "generating," "maintaining and protecting", and "encouraging" ways to motivate the learners.

1.3.3.1 Application in ESP Teaching.

The high self-esteem of the learner was of paramount importance. Feedback was positive and motivational, and rewards were introduced whenever possible. Dörnyei & Kubanyiova (2014) suggested five ways for the teacher to motivate his/ her learners to facilitate the implementation of the above model- (a) to assess the learner's present standard, (b) to create visions of the desired future for the learner (c) to picture the positive self-image of the learner, (d) to use storytelling method to guide the learner to develop visions of his/ her future, and (e) to invite successful learners to inspire the present learner. These steps were carried out on many occasions. Successful alumni were invited to the class to act as role models, and they shared their success stories based on their English writing competence.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Motivation in ESP

Arslan and Akbarov (2012) have stated that adults use a language for occupational, professional, or academic purposes. It has been observed in the case of hotel employees surveyed that their attitude toward ESP was positive, but they enjoyed EGP more owing to its universal application.

Combining the two, General English for Specific Purposes has been visioned. (Brunton, 2009). Tsao et al. (2017) show in their study that both the teachers and learners are positively motivated toward ESP because its goals instructional components are different from those of EGP. However, (Sifakis, 2003) admits that there is not sufficient literature about studies of learner motivation and attitude toward ESP.

2.2 Attitude towards ESP

The study of Kumbahr (2003) surveyed seven hundred fourteen university students from the engineering and medical departments. The thesis of Kumbahr had many goals. A critical part of this research was investigating students' attitudes towards the educational medium in colleges where English was used and in colleges where Marathi was the local language. Moreover, by analyzing the exam outcomes of the two mediums, Kumbahr tried to compare student success standards in both settings. The findings of the research corroborated the fact that the performances of the learners who used English as a tool/medium for learning were higher than those who used Marathi.

Altalib (2019) investigated the motivation of learners in specific and general language contexts using the models of Dörnyei. The learners in the specific language category had higher motivation levels and more positive attitudes than General English course learners.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research was subdivided into several components, and these are mentioned below:

- a) Selecting an appropriate sampling frame.
- b) Framing of questionnaires and semi-structured interview questions.
- c) Need Analysis of the four target groups through survey questionnaires with the respondents and interviews with respondents selected from the above groups.
- d) Selecting a control group for only pre- and post-tests and not classroom intervention
- e) Conduction of the pre-test.
- f) Course design and classroom implementation of the course.
- g) Conduction of the post-test.
- h) Study of certain chosen components of writing skill.
- i) Collection of the feedback of the course from the respondents.
- j) Final course design incorporating the suggestions of the respondents.

The present article deals with certain parts of the classroom implementation of the course and collection of the feedback on the course from the respondents.

3.2 Participants

400 students studying in the first year, after completing the English course provided in the first semester, 22 language instructors teaching language skills at different engineering colleges in West Bengal were administered a questionnaire. Their "wants", "lacks", and "necessities" (Hutchinson & Waters, 2009, pp. 55-59) were considered in designing the course. In addition, 55 operational engineers and 26 managerial engineers were also part of this triangulated study. The rationale was that the views and opinions of those who use the language were needed to compare and correlate with the present classroom teaching/ learning. Finally, 50 were selected/ enrolled for a six-month classroom teaching/ learning. A control group of forty-two students participated in pre-and post-tests but not in classroom teaching.

4. Results and Discussion

This section Tests, before and after the course, were conducted along the lines of old Cambridge exams. Both the tests were made to test the same writing genres and had the same level of difficulty. There was a gap of around six months between the two tests, and so the chances of students relying on memory were remote. The genres were the same, but not the contents.

The mean values for pre-test and post-test reveal that the students obtained better results in post-tests than in pre-testing. For this analysis, the disparity between pre-test and post-test scores is 5.18, which is impressive. The median score for the pre-test was 27, while in the post-test, it became 31. In the pre-test, mode estimates showed that the highest score, which occurred the maximum number of times, was 28 and five students scored it. The corresponding figure for the post-test was 32, and nine students scored it. In contrast, the control group showed a much smaller disparity of 0.97 between pre-test and post-test scores. The median score for the control group in the pre-test was 27.5, and the most frequent score was 29, occurring three times.

This finding again shows that more students achieved more marks after the administering of the new course. Though not directly to be taken as a measure of the levels of motivation and attitude, the feedback at the end of the post-test through a mixed methods questionnaire with closed and open-ended questions showed very positive and encouraging results as far as materials, method, usefulness in the workplace of the new writing course was concerned. On average, 80 percent agreed that the components were better and more useful than the existing course. The mean, median and mode are shown below:

Figure 1 Mean scores of pre- and post-tests

Note. The mean difference between the scores of pre and post writing tests allows us to see that students improved their writing skills through the intervention of a new course and achieved a higher result in the post-test, as in Figure 1.

Figure 2 Median scores

Note. The median equations represent the centre of the values range. This allows us to see that students improved their writing skills through the intervention of a new course and achieved a higher result in the post-test, and this can also be seen from median counting, as in Figure 2.

Note Mode indicates the amount that always occurs in the whole set. It is a way to capture any significant random variable. In the pre-test, model estimates showed that the highest score, which occurred the maximum number of times, was 28 and five students scored it. The corresponding figure for the post-test was 32, and nine students scored it. This finding again shows that more students achieved more marks after the administering of the new course.

Other than post-test results, feedback from the students was taken to assess the efficacy of the new course. A questionnaire with 11 close-ended related to materials, methodology, techniques, writing sub-skills, and 03 open-ended questions was included in this report. The answers to the close-ended questions were ordered on a Likert scale. More than 80 percent of respondents agreed on the efficacy of the new materials, methodology, techniques, and the same number admitted improvement in writing skills, including its vital components like grammar and vocabulary.

The last three questions were free writing tasks to probe deeper. The questions were as follows:

- The best things about the new course.
- The worst things about the new course.
- Two things that I think need modification in this new course.

Most students replied to questions no. 12 and 13, while question no. 14 got fewer responses. The study of open-ended queries led to the knowledge that web resources were considered quite useful. Most of the learners felt that they needed a crash or a supplementary course for improvement in their writing skills. The majority wanted more grammar practice.

Though improvement in writing ability can be attributed to many components like materials, methodology and teaching techniques, each of these components need to motivate the learners and develop a positive attitude toward ESP learning. Hence, it can be assumed that the motivation of the learners was enhanced, and their attitude towards ESP learning and the development of a new ESP course was positive. The fact that sixty students participated in a classroom instructional design over a period of six months under a faculty who was literally an outsider in their context showed their motivation and attitude levels. Further, participating in the process of new course design, interacting in the classes, completing the writing assignments, providing informal and formal feedback at each stage, writing two tests before and after the course design and that too, beyond the normal classroom hours and without any special credit or term- end exam/ test in the reckoning prove beyond doubt the enhanced motivation levels of these learners and their highly positive attitude towards improving their ESP writing skills.

5. Conclusion

Creating positive images and visions, as suggested by Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014), motivated the students. Roleplays proved to be an easy technique to emphasize this aspect. Once again, the importance of motivation and attitude, as Gardner (1985)

showed, was reinforced. 50 students participated in 60 extra hours of classroom instruction beyond their college hours. The students were initially a bit reluctant because of their linguistic ability and the fact that the instructor was an outsider. However, very soon, the changes in instructional design, materials, assessment, and methodology brought about a lot of positive changes, and they started interacting a lot and freely. The majority of the students showed a positive attitude toward error. They wanted to learn about and rectify those. Granting sufficient time and freedom to the linguistically weak students helped the researcher reach out to them better. No force was applied for immediate production. Fluency was given priority in the initial stages and accuracy in the final stages. This strategy ensured greater participation by way of completion of writing tasks. Whatever be the level of teaching, motivation and a positive attitude towards the target language are always indispensable. Not much attention is paid to motivation and attitude in the ESP context, ostensibly because ESP itself is highly motivating. That is not the ideal approach.

6. Limitations of the study

The number of participants in the classroom was only fifty. It was not easy to gather participants for additional classes for a non-engineering curriculum for six long months. The motivation and attitude of teachers is also an important component of any English teaching, including ESP. This was not covered by this study. It also did not measure the motivation and attitude of learners because the focus of the study was the implementation of the tenets of motivation and attitude in the classroom. However, it was assumed that feedback about the materials, method and usefulness of the new writing course could prove these.

7. Future Implications

The study can be utilised by any ESP practitioner both in the context of classroom teaching and ESP course design. As teachers, we should not take it for granted when it comes to the motivation and attitude of the learners toward ESP on the assumption that ESP itself is motivating. This study can be sort of ready reference as theories have been identified here and practically implemented. It is hoped that further research will be carried out not only on these but other theories related to this domain. Teacher motivation and attitude toward ESP need also to be researched for a holistic developmental of ESP teaching/ learning.

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Appendix- A

Post-test feedback (Student questionnaire)

Statement	Response
1. The materials of this new course in English writing skills improved my writing skills.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
2. The materials of this new course in English writing skills were appropriate and relevant.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
3. The materials of this new course in English writing skills were graded and organized.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
4. The materials of this new course in English writing skills provided written practice in all the selected genres.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
5. The materials of this new course in English writing skills were interesting and motivating.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
6. Teaching techniques/ methodology of this new course in English writing skills improved my writing skills.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
7. This new writing course improved my English grammar.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
8. This new writing course improved my English vocabulary	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
9. The new English writing course would help me in the workplace.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say

10. Writing a blog is useful.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
11. Google Group is useful for developing writing skills.	Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't say
12. The best things about the new course	Free writing
13. The worst things about the new course	Free writing
14. Two things that I think need modification in this new course.	Free writing

Appendix- B**Pre-test writing skill question paper**

The numbers in brackets indicate full marks. You will get 2 hours to complete the three writing tasks given below:

Question 1

The following two graphs (graphs were attached) show the growth of the Indian manufacturing and services sector in terms of exports and imports between 2000 to 2010. Using the information given in the graphs, write a report of the country's exports and imports along with the trade balance in 300 words. [15]

Question 2

You work for Techjig Inc, which manufactures high-end mobile tablets. Your company is going to launch a new tablet whose retail price would be 50 thousand in Indian currency. Write a sales letter which would be sent to the dealers/ distributors urging them to start placing orders with your company immediately. You may include their profit- margin, the features and benefits of the product, the marketing support that will be provided. [15]

Question 3

You are the IT Head of your organization. Your Managing Director wants the website of the organization to be revamped and improved and so has asked you to submit a proposal. Write a proposal for the new website. You may include the strengths and weaknesses of the existing website, the changes and improvements that you suggest, and the benefits of the organization by incorporating the changes. [15]

Appendix- C**Post-test writing skill question paper**

The numbers in brackets indicate full marks. You will get 2 hours to complete the three writing tasks given below:

Question 1

The following two pie charts (pie charts attached) show the budgets of two states- Kerala and West Bengal- regarding health, higher education, and infrastructure development for the financial year 2017-18. Using the information given in the pie- charts, compare the budgets of the two states within 300 words. [15].

Question 2

You work for Technocraft Inc, which manufactures high-end mobile handsets. Your company is going to launch a new mobile handset whose retail price would be 40 thousand in Indian currency. Write a sales letter which would be sent to the dealers/ distributors urging them to start placing orders with your company immediately. You may include their profit- margin, the features and benefits of the product, the marketing support that will be provided.[15]

Question 3

You are the Project Head of an IT firm headquartered in Hyderabad. Your organization has five offices. You want to conduct a 6-day training on new technology. But you are not getting all the desired number of the technical staff for training because their department heads are not willing to release so many personnel for 6 days at a stretch and because such an exercise would involve a lot of expenditure by way of travel, food, and lodging costs. Write a proposal arguing the pros and cons of conducting online training sessions with implications that benefits would be more than the cons. [15]

Appendix- D

Scoring key for pre and post writing tests. (Adapted from Hyland, 2003, p. 228)

Marks Characteristics

Above 90 %	Central idea- Sufficient clarity Organization- Sufficiently coherent and logical Vocabulary- Appropriate and a large repertoire. Mechanics- Hardly any spelling or punctuation errors.
70-90 %	Central idea- Fair amount of clarity Organization- Largely coherent and logical Vocabulary- Appropriate Mechanics- A few spelling or punctuation errors.
50- 70 %	Central idea- Expressed, but clarity blurred Organization- Some problems with coherence and logical structure. Vocabulary- Moderate Mechanics- Many spelling or punctuation errors.
30-50%	Central idea- Not conveying or expressing the task. Organization- Poor with serious coherence issues. Vocabulary- Poor with a very narrow repertoire. Mechanics-Consistent spelling or punctuation errors.
Below 30%	Central idea- Idea is not communicated at all. Organization- Very poor and hardly any coherence and logical structure. Vocabulary- Very poor and much below the target level. Mechanics- Spelling or punctuation errors throughout.